

Information Literacy in Promoting e-Resources and its Empowerment for LIS Professionals

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INFORMATION LITERACY AND TECHNOLOGY LITERACY; IN A DIGITAL WORLD

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Abstract:

{The article views the changes that are taking in the world particularly in learning environment. Knowledge of Information, Technology and Digital Libraries are to be viewed to develop and utilize new frameworks, skills, tools and value systems for the end-users.. Innovations in technology can improve literacy programmes and accelerate the spread of literacy. Alternative strategies need to be identified to ensure greater learning effectiveness and meet the literacy needs of masses of people in a timely and economical manner. It is a tool to improve literacy programmes, raise awareness about the literacy problems and reach a vast number of unreached illiterates with technology as it deals not only with textual literacy, but also with visual literacy}.

Key words: *Information Literacy, Technology, Learning, Skills*

Introduction

Information literacy has become an important skill for students to gain before they enter real world, Information literacy can be defined as being able to recognize when information is needed and have the ability to locate, evaluate, and use it effectively. In the past there was one main way to get information and it was by going to a library and finding a published source. Technology has made more and more information readily available. The digital age has brought about new sources that in the past would never have been even thought of. The Internet provides us with a background on almost any topic imaginable. To be literate one must find the information in a reasonable amount time. Because there is so much information pinpointing what you need and what you don't has become a necessary skill. Using the correct search engine and searching with the correct specifications could save you hours by locating the correct information. We need to help our students be successful in the 21st century in which we now live is constantly changing. We have transitioned from using desktop-based applications to new online tools, and ultimately we are able to work differently.

Objectives of the study

- To recognize the need for information ,and to evaluate, organize ,interpret and communicate information in all it's formats;
- Use technology tools to enhance, increase productivity and promote creativity;
- Apply information and technology competencies to learning in the context areas;
- Enables individuals to develop skills for learning throughout life;
- Encompasses the effective use of multiple information technologies and formats.

Definition of Information literacy:

Information literacy has been defined as a set of abilities requiring individual's to recognize when information is needed and have the ability to locate, evaluate, and use effectively the needed information (American Library Association, 1989). The Association of College and Research Libraries (ACRL) extends this definition by stating that information literacy forms the basis for lifelong learning (2000a). The importance of lifelong learning and preparing students for the future is also stressed by The Association to Advance Collegiate Schools of Business (AACSB) in its Preamble to Eligibility Procedures and Standards for Business Accreditation (2003): As part of each institution's effort to prepare its students for future careers, it should provide a total educational experience that emphasizes conceptual reasoning, problem-solving skills, and preparation for lifelong learning.

Information and Technology Literacy:

In today's context information literacy three things are very important as shown in the fig no.1:

Fig No: 1 Unified Conceptual Framework

The skills essential to access, evaluate, and use information and technology are to be identified. In the unified conceptual framework it demonstrates:

- A progression from the physical access skills for the use of media and technology,
- To the intellectual access skills of information use,
- To skills and attitudes for learning independently and finally
- The skills needed for working responsibly and productively within groups.

Characteristics of Information Literacy

1. It stresses the basic concepts of how information is organized; the formats it comes in, and the structures used by different disciplines to record and transmit information;
2. Knowledge of these broader ideas provides an information-literate user with a map of information structures;
3. The map in turn represents the information landscape through which the researcher will navigate.

Knowledge of the information search process and environment brings an awareness of the pitfalls and side roads that surface during information voyages;

4. Information-literate searchers are conscious of the research process as it takes place;
5. Information literacy encompasses computer literacy and media literacy. A computer-literate person can manipulate electronic information tools to gain access to information. Computers are part of the wider category of information tools and require their own special search methodologies.

How Does it differ from Information Literacy, Technology Literacy, and Digital Literacy

Technology Literacy:

As technology involves more than computers and the Internet, technological literacy involves more than hands-on skill in using technology. Certainly, knowing how to use information technology is increasingly important in our knowledge society, we must also be able to use other devices, like microwaves, copying machines, and self-service gas pumps that have become part of everyday life at home, at work, or in the community. However, the ability to use technology is only one part of technological literacy. This type of technological literacy would include knowledge about the details of individual technologies and about the process of technology development. It would also include a holistic understanding of the historical and cultural context of technology and adaptability based on initiative and resourceful thinking. Finally, enduring, inherent technological literacy would include our generalized competencies:

- Accommodate and cope with rapid and continuous technological change;
- Generate creative and innovative solutions for technological problems;
- Act through technological knowledge both effectively and efficiently; and
- Assess technology and its involvement with the human life world judiciously.

These elements are mirrored in other descriptions of technological Literacy. characterizes technological literacy as consisting of knowledge and skills. Broad knowledge areas include problems

that might be solved with technology, important technologies, social and cultural effects of technology, prerequisite knowledge from other disciplines (e.g., math), and the form or structure of technological knowledge.

Standards for Technological Literacy

- **The Nature of Technology** .characteristics and scope of technology; core concepts of technology; the relationships among technologies and connections between technology and other fields;
- **Technology and Society** .cultural, social, economic, and political effects of technology; effects of technology on the environment; role of society in the development and use of technology; influence of technology on history;
- **Design**. Attributes of design; engineering design; role of troubleshooting, research and development, invention and innovation, experimentation in problem solving.
- **Abilities for a Technological World**. apply the design process; use and maintain technological products and systems; assess the impact of products and systems
- **The Designed World**. medical technologies; agricultural and related biotechnologies; energy and power technologies; information and communication technologies ;transportation technologies; manufacturing technologies; construction technologies

Information Literacy in Digital Age:

It is a major component of information literacy. It helps users cope with information from a variety of electronic formats and provides techniques and methods of collecting digital resources. It creates Awareness of issues like copyright and intellectual property rights in electronic nvironment.Digital literacy includes the ability to understand the power of images and sounds, to recognize and use that power, to manipulate and transform digital media, to distribute them pervasively and to easily adopt them to new forms. The most essential aspect of digital literacy is the ability to make informed judge ments about what is found online, for unlike conventional media, much digital information is unfiltered by editors and open to the contribution of all.

Why Focus On Digital Literacy

- Digital Literacy is a 21st century skill
- Educators may need to re think the ways that we conceptualize learning and literacy
- We Employ technology to make difficult and challenging things, so enticing and engaging that learners will be hooked and believe the tasks are worthy of effort.
- It is important to take advantage of the educational potential of these tools

Information literacy skills in Digital Era:

Codification of information in digital form is a predominant practice in this time, new skills are needed to drive the technology to search for, organize, manage information and use it to solve

problems. As the internet is becoming a mostly used communication tool, information literacy often understood as digital literacy. Computer literacy is an essential component of information literacy, but there are differences between computer literacy, media literacy and information literacy. Digital information literacy as consisting of the two following elements:

- Basic information and communication technology (ICT) skills: use of program applications and search, locate, transform and control of information from different digital sources:
- Advanced skills to secure a creative and critical use of digital tools and media Digital literacy thus imply basic ICT skills and information literacy.

In another way digital information literacy may proceed as per the following line of action: Access-Interpret-Create. For better understanding of the terms following points should be kept in mind.

- **Access :**
 - o Understand how digital information is created, stored and transported; and how to establish Internet connectivity and a network.
 - o Know how to use search techniques to find digital information
- **Interpret:**
 - o Be able to identify a range of digital formats i.e. file formats available and their uses:
 - o Understand copyright as well as other related issues like Digital Rights Management etc. as it is applied to digital objects.
- **Create:**
 - o Be able to use different data capturing technologies.
 - o Be able to edit text, audio, images and videos.
 - o Know the ways to publish digital information.

Conclusion

The idea of information literacy, broadly deepened as the ability to recognize information needs and to identify, evaluate and use information electively, has been of growing concern in the education sectors for a number of years; whilst in the workplace, employers and managers have perhaps attended more to the need for computer and information technology skills. As information technology becomes more seamless and user-friendly, it is likely that attention will shift more clearly to questions of how people are actually interacting with, and using, the information which technology makes available. In organizations where users continue to struggle with information technology, the perennial need to make decisions, problem-solve and research, also suggests the need for employees to be able to deal with information per se as being of primary importance. Information literacy and its associated terminology should not be confused with popular terms and contemporaneous phrases

appearing in the literature, such as “computer literacy,” “IT literacy,” and “informatics.” These terms refer to a specific range of skills encompassing diverse information and communication technologies, such as e-mail, desktop applications, and network environment. Information literacy competency is broader in scope than skillful use of technological tools. An individual may be computer literate and skilled at working in an electronic environment but may not necessarily be information literate.

References:

1. Johnston, B., & Webber, S. (2003). Information literacy in higher education: A review and case study. *Studies in Higher Education*, 28,335–352;
2. Lindstrom, J., & Shonrock, D. D. (2006). Faculty–librarian collaboration to achieve integration of information literacy. *Reference and User Services Quarterly*, 46, 18–23;
3. Bruce, C. (1997). The relational approach: a new model for information literacy. *The New Review of Information and Library Research*, 3, 1–22;
4. McCrank, L. J. (1992). Academic programs for information literacy: theory and structure. *Reference Quarterly*, 31(4), 485–498.

